

Interfejsy analogowe CoCPU

$$V_{in} := \begin{bmatrix} 32 \\ 18 \\ 5,5 \end{bmatrix} \text{ V}$$

$$R_{g1} := 91 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$R_d := 13 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$R_{p1} := R_{g1} = 91000 \Omega$$

$$R_{g2} := 91 \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$R_{p2} := \frac{R_{g1} \cdot R_{g2}}{R_{g1} + R_{g2}} = 45500 \Omega$$

$$R_{g3} := 5100 \Omega$$

$$R_{p3} := \frac{R_{g1} \cdot R_{g3}}{R_{g1} + R_{g3}} = 4829,3444 \Omega$$

$$V_{out1} := V_{in1} \cdot \left(\frac{R_d}{R_{g1} + R_d} \right) = 4 \text{ V}$$

$$V_{out2} := V_{in2} \cdot \left(\frac{R_d}{R_{p2} + R_d} \right) = 4 \text{ V}$$

$$V_{out3} := V_{in3} \cdot \left(\frac{R_d}{R_{p3} + R_d} \right) = 4,0102 \text{ V}$$

$$I_{dz1} := \frac{V_{in1}}{R_{g1} + R_d} = 0,3077 \text{ mA}$$

$$I_{dz2} := \frac{V_{in2}}{R_{p2} + R_d} = 0,3077 \text{ mA}$$

$$I_{dz3} := \frac{V_{in3}}{R_{p3} + R_d} = 0,3085 \text{ mA}$$

$$P_{max} := \frac{V_{in1}^2}{R_{g1}} = 15,146 \text{ mW}$$

$$Z_{we} := \begin{bmatrix} R_{g1} + R_d \\ R_{p2} + R_d \\ R_{p3} + R_d \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 104 \\ 58,5 \\ 17,829 \end{bmatrix} \text{ k}\Omega$$

$$Z_{eqv} := \frac{R_{p3} \cdot R_d}{R_{p3} + R_d} = 3521,244 \Omega$$

$$f_{filtr} := 2,5 \text{ kHz}$$

$$C_{min} := \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot Z_{eqv} \cdot f_{filtr}} = 18,079 \text{ nF}$$

$$C := 47 \text{ nF}$$

$$f_{3db} := \frac{1}{2 \cdot \pi \cdot C \cdot Z_{eqv}} = 961,67 \text{ Hz}$$

Zakres filtru 297Hz ... 961Hz